

IMPACT OF WORK LIFE BALANCE OF EMPLOYEES IN HOSPITAL INDUSTRY IN INDIA- A CASE STUDY OF APOLLO HOSPITALS, VISAKHAPATNAM

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Abstract

Purpose: The main purpose of this study is to identifying Work Life Balance of Employees in Hospital Industry in India- A Case Study of Apollo Hospitals, Visakhapatnam of Andhra Pradesh.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The researcher had focused his attention on aimed to explore the role of perceived work-life balance and job satisfaction in developing commitment among hospital employees. In addition to that, gender difference is also taken into consideration to draw concrete conclusion. The study is quantitative in nature. Based on the literature review it is proposed that work-life balance and satisfaction will be significantly contributing in developing commitment among the chosen respondents. Results revealed a moderate level of work-life balance, job satisfaction and organizational commitment among the chosen employees. Significant relationship is found between work-life balance and job satisfaction. **Originality/Value.** In this study we used in Descriptive Research tools to be used like ANOVA, for Work interfering family life and family interfering work life are found positively related with organizational commitment. Male and female respondent are found significantly different in their level of commitment, perceived work interfering family life and perceived family interfering work life. **Findings:** Work-life balance is about finding the right balance between one's work and one's life (i.e. life outside work) and about feeling comfortable with both work and non- work commitments. Many people find it difficult to manage their time in a way that is healthy for their work as well as for their personal life (Vlems, 2005). This may not be because they are poor at time management, but largely because a good part of the time is not theirs. It belongs to the organization. But do employees have to crowd out other activities that are important in their lives just to satisfy the boss? Achieving the right balance is something very personal, because we all have different priorities in life.

Keywords: Work-Life Balance, Job Satisfaction, Hospital, Relationship, Family.

1. INTRODUCTION

Work-life balance is about finding a way to manage the demands of your work or study with your personal life and the things that 'top you up'. A good work-life balance means you can be happy and productive at work and also have time for yourself and your family. Man is a social animal, needs time for self, family and society to satisfy their various needs. An individual spends more than eight hours a day in office, remaining is spent in travel to and from office, and with family and friends. Very little time is available for attending to his/her personal needs or grooming. In today's highly competitive environment people are giving more importance to their work, by working hard, spending more time at the office, learning and adapting to the changing business environment to stay relevant. The quality of the time spent by people with their family, friends or for themselves would help the individuals to relax, refocus and perform better in their jobs. This would automatically benefit the organizations in enhancing the overall organizations performance. Work-life balance is a concept including proper

prioritizing between “work” (career and ambition) and “lifestyle” (Health, pleasure, leisure, family and spiritual development/meditation). This study aims at understanding the current work– life balance scenario in health-care Industry. And the efforts of organization in improving the work life balance. The descriptive study was carried out in the city of Vishakhapatnam. At the present time all the companies are trying to maintain standards, deliver quality goods on time and attain reputation and recognition for their business organization along with maintaining customer satisfaction.

Despite the resounding evidence that working long hours can be harmful to both employees and employers, many professionals still struggle to overcome their assumptions — and their deeply-ingrained habits — around work hours. What does it take to free yourself from these unhealthy patterns and reach a more sustainable, rewarding work-life balance? To explore this question, we conducted almost 200 in-depth interviews with 78 professionals from the London offices of a global law firm and an accounting firm.

We spoke with an equal number of men and women, and most of the interviewees were between 30 and 50 years old, with at least one dependent child, and in either middle or senior management roles. To with stand in the global market or competition the companies are demanding and anticipating their employees acquire skills, to be updated with latest technology and to work more in order to achieve their targets. Similarly the employees are demanding more support from the employers in terms of time and resource to enrich their social life. In most cases, while trying to attain the targets, work schedule creates more burden and stress to the employees which lead to imbalance of their work and personal life as a result it creates fear and frustration to the employee. At a high level, our research showed that achieving better balance between professional and personal priorities boils down to a combination of reflexivity — or questioning assumptions to increase self-awareness — and intentional role redefinition. Importantly, our research suggests that this is not a one-time fix, but rather, a cycle that we must engage in continuously as our circumstances and priorities evolve. This cycle is made up of five distinct steps.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- ❖ **Clark SC** (2000) work life balance is important for psychological well-being, high self-esteem, satisfaction and harmony between work and life indicates the work life balance. Greenhaus et al. (2003) says that work family balance includes involvement, time and satisfaction balance.
- ❖ Griffin, Hogan, Lambert, Tucker-Gail & Baker (2010) defines job stress as “a worker’s feelings of job related tension, anxiety, frustration, worry, emotional exhaustion, and distress.”
- ❖ **R. Baral & S. Bhargava**, (2011), Family well-being oriented welfare programmes have been initiated by employers in India which was a matter of concern since Industrialization. But the policies and practices are best put in use in software and service sectors. Clark (2000) defines work life balance as “satisfaction and good functioning at work and home, with a minimum of role conflict.” Voydanoff (2005) defines it as “global assessment that work and family resources are sufficient to meet work and family demands such that participation is effective in both domains.”
- ❖ **Abhishek Raj & Pushkar Singh** (2019), the subsidy and profitability of connotation put your faith in exhibition and duty of its representatives. Each representative has an individual and skillful life expectancy; mutually these are exceptionally inflexible to isolate. They must always be circulated and performed on the off case that if an agency offers to oblige better productivity and higher responsibility from members instead. An individual may do this while he or she has a wonderful life into and out of the employment.
- ❖ **Vasumathi.A** (2018), the survey of writing on work life parity of ladies representatives has stood illustrated in standpoint on its expanded prevalence thru the momentous target to need for bourgeoning of society. WLB is a significant worry for ladies representatives in the present situation, as broadened hours of work in association pulls ladies representatives' efficiency and stint which they really intended to commit to their kinfolk loop.
- ❖ **Fathima Aroosiya** (2013), as per paper the working ladies have double jobs to be specific job in the working spot and job at home in the advanced economy. This prompts face more troubles in the life of working ladies so as to be increasingly powerful in their double life while the working men have less weight contrasting and working ladies. In the example size was 100 working ladies particularly the educators of government school and representatives in divisional secretariat which comprise of 15 inquiries. Information was exposed to graphic measurements. The consequences of the examination uncovered that the degree of work life equalization of working ladies was low level.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- ❖ To study and understand the concept of “work- life balance” in Apollo hospital, health city, Vishakhapatnam.
- ❖ To assess the current work-life balance practices and policies in place at Apollo hospitals and identify areas for improvement.

- ❖ To gather and analyze data on the impact of work-life balance on employee satisfaction, engagement and performance.
- ❖ To develop and implement strategies and initiatives that promote work-life balance and support employee well-being, such as flexible work arrangements, stress management programs and employee wellness initiatives.
- ❖ To evaluate the effectiveness of the strategies and initiatives implemented and make recommendations for future improvements.
- ❖ To create awareness among employees about the importance of work-life balance and encourage them to take steps to maintain a healthy work-life balance.
- ❖ To collaborate with various departments and stakeholders within Apollo hospitals to create a holistic approach to work-life balance that addresses the needs of employees at all levels of the organization.

1. Hypothesis of the Study:

Ho: There is no significance difference between quality time spent with family and friends and satisfaction with activities.

H1: There is significance difference between quality time spent with family and friends and satisfaction with activities.

Ho: There is no influence of work environment on employee fatigue.

H1: There is influence of work environment on employee fatigue.

2. Need For The Study

Work-life balance is all about creating, building and maintaining a perfect balance between the professional and personal responsibilities. Work –life balance has been identified as an important practice to develop a healthy work environment which enables to retain the employees and increase their productivity.

The work-life conflicts have increased now-a-days comparing to the past and it may be due to the competing/ challenging responsibilities of the workers such as work, parents (elderly), children, household works, spouse which causes stress to an employee. The work life conflict is a serious problem which can impact an individual, his/ her family, the community they belong to and the company they are working in.

3. Methodology of the Study:

Methodology is a set of practices and rules from which specific methods or procedures may be acquired to either solve or interpret problem relating to a specific field. The methodology includes the respective methods of data collection, tools and various sample procedures.

Data Collection: Data can be collected either through primary technique or secondary data collection technique.

Primary Data: primary data is the first hand data collected directly by the researcher to find the answers for his research problem. This kind of data is original in nature. The tool or technique used for collecting primary data is in the form of structured questionnaire.

Questionnaire: A questionnaire consists of a set of questions relating to the research which is filled by the respondents. A questionnaire helps in conducting the survey and directly collects the information from respondents.

Secondary Data: secondary data is that kind of data which has already been collected by some other researcher i.e. the data is readily available. The secondary data collected for my study was obtained from company's website, magazines, journals and report books.

Population and Samplings: The sample for the study was chosen by means of convenience sampling techniques. As the study was intended to know about the work-life balance of the employees working at Apollo hospitals, health city, it was decided not to restrict the study to a particular department. Hence the sample covers nurses from all departments and administration staff.

Sampling Representation: The survey is conducted by considering respondents based on following sample representation.

Sample from nurses–60

Sample from admin staff & Support Staff–40

Data Analysis: A careful analysis has been done on the data which has been obtained through tabulations and graphical presentations.

Conclusions are drawn on the study to suggest the company, which can be implemented for company's betterment.

4. Limitations of the Study:

A good report describes and explains the results derived through the study. As a result whatever limitations occur in the study also creeps into the report and become the limitations of the report.

Every project has its own limitations and so did mine. I have listed a few of the limitations of my study below:

- ❖ Study was limited to "Apollo hospitals, health city, Vishakhapatnam only. Therefore, the results may not be capable for universal application.
- ❖ Interaction with nurses and other employees was very restricted because of their busy work schedule.
- ❖ The study does not cover all the departments like, doctors, technicians, consultants; it is only confined to nurses from various departments and administration staff.
- ❖ The data collected cannot be asserted to be free from errors as majority of the respondents being nurses and admin staff showed some biasness while providing the relevant data relating my study.
- ❖ The sample size was confined to 100 only. Out of 100, 60 are nurses and 40 are admin staff as I have collected the information from only day shift employees i.e. from 9:00AM to 6:00PM because of time constrains and their busy schedule in the health care industry.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table No 1: Demographic Information of Administration Staff

Variable	Factors	No. of Respondents	Percent in total
Age	Less than 30 years	35	35%
	31-45 years	55	55%
	Above 45 years	20	20%
Gender	Male	65	65%
	Female	35	35%
	Others	0	0
Education qualification	Ssc/Inter	0	0%
	Graduation	82	85%
	Others	15	15%
Location	Urban	75	75%
	Rural	0	0%
	Semi Urban	25	25%
Marital status	Single	45	45%
	Married	55	55%
	Others	0	0%
Family size	Less Than 3 Members	40	40%
	4-6 Members	40	40%
	More Than 6 Members	20	20%
Annual income	1-2 Lakh	25	25%
	2-3 Lakh	35	35%
	More Than 3 Lakh	40	40%
Experience	1 month-4 Years	25	25%
	4-6 Years	15	15%
	More Than 6 Years	60	60%

Interpretation:

From the above table and bar chart, it is analyzed that majority of the respondents are below 30 years of age and this set of employees are to be retained as they can still work for a longer time.

It is analyzed that most of the respondents in admin department are male who have completed their inter and are well educated in their field and more than 50% of respondents belong to urban areas and 50% of respondents are from rural areas. It is understood that majority of the employees in admin department are married and therefore they have more responsibilities towards their family and it is important for them to understand the importance of work life balance to give their whole as an individual to the organization as well as to his family. The data suggests that a significant portion of employees have family responsibilities that could affect their work-life balance. 40% of employees have small families, 40% have moderate-sized families, and 20% have large families, indicating varying levels of family-related obligations. Employers may need to consider these family responsibilities when designing work policies and benefits to support their employees 'work-life balance. The majority of employees receive a salary of more than 2 lakh per annum, with 40% of employees earning more than 3 lakh per annum. This may indicate that employees have sufficient financial resources to support their work-life balance needs, such as child care or leisure activities. However, it's important to note that the data does not directly measure the extent to which employees' salaries affect their work-life balance. It also analyzes that Apollo hospital consists of employees with a wide range of experience, starting from a fresher to employees who have experience of working for more than 10 years.

Administration Staff Perspective of Work Life Balance:

Variable	Factors	No. of Respondents	Percent in total
Working hours	More than 14 hours	0	0%
	More than 12 hours	5	5%
	More than 10 hours	20	20%
	More than 8 hours	75	75%
	Less than 8 hours	0	0%
Intervals	Never	5	5%
	Rarely	30	30%
	Sometimes	50	50%
	Often	0	0%
	Always	15	15%
Quality time	Never	15	15%
	Rarely	20	20%
	Sometimes	55	55%
	Often	5	5%
	Always	5	5%
Work environment	Never	5	5%
	Rarely	5	5%
	Sometimes	5	5%
	Often	20	20%
	Always	65	65%
Initiatives	Never	0	0%
	Rarely	25	25%
	Sometimes	55	55%
	Often	0	0%
	Always	20	20%
Satisfaction with activities	Strongly Dissatisfied	0	0%
	Dissatisfied	10	10%
	Moderately	15	15%
	Satisfied	55	55%
	Strongly Satisfied	20	20%

Tired And Exhausted	Never	10	10%
	Rarely	10	10%
	Sometimes	70	70%
	Often	10	10%
	Always	0	0%

Quality Time Spent with Family and Friends and Satisfaction with Activities:

Descriptives									
SATISFACTION									
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum	Between-Component Variance
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound			
1	15	2.33	.488	.126	2.06	2.60	2	3	
2	20	3.50	.513	.115	3.26	3.74	3	4	
3	55	4.18	.389	.052	4.08	4.29	4	5	
4	5	5.00	.000	.000	5.00	5.00	5	5	
5	5	5.00	.000	.000	5.00	5.00	5	5	
Total	100	3.85	.857	.086	3.68	4.02	2	5	
Model	Fixed Effects		.417	.042	3.77	3.93			
	Random Effects			.573	2.26	5.44			.882

Test of Homogeneity of Variances			
SATISFACTION			
Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
12.388	4	95	.000

ANOVA					
SATISFACTION					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	56.235	4	14.059	80.870	.000
Within Groups	16.515	95	.174		
Total	72.750	99			

Interpretation:

The above table demonstrates ANOVA with respect to satisfaction with activities in quality time. It is being observed that there is a significant impact of satisfaction with activities on quality time.

(Sig. $p = 0.000 < 0.05$)

Work Environment on Employee Fatigue:

Descriptives									
FATIQUE									
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum	Between-Component Variance
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound			
1	5	1.00	.000	.000	1.00	1.00	1	1	
2	5	1.00	.000	.000	1.00	1.00	1	1	
3	5	2.00	.000	.000	2.00	2.00	2	2	
4	20	2.75	.444	.099	2.54	2.96	2	3	
5	65	3.15	.364	.045	3.06	3.24	3	4	
Total	100	2.80	.752	.075	2.65	2.95	1	4	
Model	Fixed Effects		.359	.036	2.73	2.87			
	Random Effects			.621	1.08	4.52			.816

Test of Homogeneity of Variances			
FATIGUE			
Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
5.963	4	95	.000

ANOVA					
FATIGUE					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	43.788	4	10.947	85.163	.000
Within Groups	12.212	95	.129		
Total	56.000	99			

Interpretation:

The above table demonstrates ANOVA with respect to tired and exhausted in work environment.

It is being observed that there is a significant impact of tired and exhausted on work environment.

(Sig. $p = 0.000 < 0.05$)

CONCLUSION

Healthcare has become one of India's largest sectors - both in terms of revenue and employment. The Indian health care sector is growing at a brisk pace due to its strengthening coverage, services and increasing expenditure by public as well private players.

Indian healthcare delivery system is categorized into two major components - public and private. The Government, i.e. public healthcare system comprises limited secondary and tertiary care institutions in key cities and focuses on providing basic healthcare facilities in the form of primary health care centers (PHCs) in rural areas. The private sector provides majority of secondary, tertiary and quaternary care institutions with a major concentration in metros, tier I and tier II cities.

The healthcare sector is at the epicenter of this unprecedented global pandemic challenge, and the private sector has risen to the occasion, by offering to the government all the support it needs, be it testing support preparing isolation beds for the treatment of covid-19 positive patients or deploying equipment and staff in identified nodal hospitals.

Apollo Hospitals was the forerunner of integrated healthcare in Asia, as well as globally. Over the past three decades Apollo Hospitals' transformative journey has forged a legacy of excellence in Indian healthcare. The Group has continuously set the agenda and led by example in the blossoming private healthcare space and also developed centers of excellence in Cardiac Sciences, Orthopedics, Neurosciences, Emergency Care, Cancer and Organ Transplantation. Along with excellence the Apollo philosophy rests on the pillars of technological superiority, a warm patient-centric approach, a clear and distinct cost advantage and an edge in forward-looking research.

Work-life balance is about finding the right balance between one's work and one's life (i.e. life outside work) and about feeling comfortable with both work and non-work commitments. Many people find it difficult to manage their time in a way that is healthy for their work as well as for their personal life (Vleems, 2005). This may not be because they are poor at time management, but largely because a good part of the time is not theirs. It belongs to the organization. But do employees have to crowd out other activities that are important in their lives just to satisfy the boss? Achieving the right balance is something very personal, because we all have different priorities in life.

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